

STUDY ON CURING PROCESS OPTIMIZATION OF EXTRA-THICK CARBON FIBER REINFORCED EPOXY RESIN MATRIX COMPOSITES AND THEIR PROPERTIES

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Abstract

With the purpose of determining suitable curing process cycle of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy resin composites with extra thickness, the recommended curing cycle was firstly analyzed with embedding thermal couples in the composites. Based on the systematically study on curing properties of prepregs, some curing cycle optimizations with low heating rates within recommended curing cycle was applied, and the corresponding cured composites were inspected with ultrasonic C-scan and internal quality analysis. The result exhibits that it shows much better temperature uniformity and controllable curing react exotherm during the optimized curing process. And all the composites exhibit good quality.

1. Introduction

In thermal processing of large or complex composite structures, such as autoclave or oven curing, it's crucial to the optimize the curing profile. Usually the temperature in such composite parts will tend to go outside the bounds of the specified cure cycle due to exotherm and the low heat conduction of prepreg, and finally result in overheated, even lead to degradation or combustion. Additionally, the badly nonuniform temperature distribution across the thickness is an important factor in determining residual stresses, fiber volume content or final deformation of the structure [1-3].

Aiming to obtaining qualified composite structure, the optimizations of thick composite have been carried out by various groups over the years in both academia and industry [1,3-10]. It has been found that it is usually difficult and complex to optimize the curing cycle profile by sophisticate theoretical model due to the low thermal conductivity, exotherm and anisotropy of thermoset prepregs. S.R. White applied the "steps-curing" method to extra-thick composite manufacturing, and composites structures with enhanced quality has been obtained [2], however, the curing cycle of "steps-curing" is too time-consumed. Meanwhile, this processing only can be applied for some certain prepregs, because different material systems usually exhibit distinguish curing behaviors attributing to different chemical reaction and rheology behaviors of thermoset resin system. Additionally, many other processing methods for extra-thick have been reported, these methods need either special equipment or novel resin systems, can't be directly applied in ordinary composites manufacturing process [11-15]. It is valuable to develop processing methods based on the common curing equipment via relatively simple curing cycles.

With the purpose to determine and verify suitable optimized curing cycle profiles for one novel epoxy resin matrixed carbon fiber reinforced prepreg, work presented in this paper analyzed the temperature distribution within extra-thick composite laminations with the thickness of 16 and 32 mm, different optimized curing processing has been carried out and quality of cured composites have been characterized, based on comparison of processing feasibility and overall composite characters, optimized curing cycles have been purposed for this epoxy matrixed prepreg.

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2. Experiment and characterization

2.1 Thermal and rheology analysis

The carbon fiber reinforced high temperature cured epoxy prepreg (UD tape), supplied by Cytec Co., USA. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was conducted on a TA-Q100 analyzer at a heating rate of 10 °C/min in a nitrogen atmosphere and at a flow rate of 50 cm³/min. Complex viscosity was performed on a TA-AR 2000 rheometer using the test specimen disks with diameter of 25 mm and thickness of 1.2 mm, which were prepared by compression molding of the prepreg at room temperature. The compacted disk was subsequently loaded in the rheometer fixed with 25 mm diameter parallel plates. The top plate was oscillated at a fixed strain of 5% and a fixed angular frequency of 10 rad/s

whereas the lower plate was attached to a transducer, which was used to record the resultant torque. For the testing of dynamic thermal melt complex viscosity, the test specimens were scanned from 50 °C at a heating rate of 4 °C/min, in which the melt viscosity (η^* , complex viscosity as a function of time) was determined.

2.2 In process temperature measuring and quality evaluation of composite plates

In process temperature was measured by CHINO-3/5 thermal couples (CHINO Co., Japan), all the composites were cured via autoclave ASC-3900 (ACS Co., USA) with temperature uniformity of $\pm 5.6^\circ\text{C}$ and pressure uniformity of $\pm 0.02\text{Mpa}$. in this work, five composite laminations with thickness of 16 and 32 mm were manufactured (named with 16-1#, 16-2#, 32-1#, 32-2# and 32-3# respectively, the manufacturing process was conducted as follow:

- 1) Dimensions of composite laminations is 600×600 mm with thickness of 16 and 32 mm and lay-up sequence of quasi-isotropic; A pair of thermal couples were placed in the center of laminations every other 22 ply prepregs (thermal couples were also placed on the top and bottom of laminations).
- 2) Bagging method: the composites were placed on a 25.4 mm (1") thick aluminum tooling and bagged as shown in the Figure 1.
- 3) Curing processing of thick composite laminations: 5 experiments were conducted for different curing cycle conditions as shown in Table 1.
- 4) Evaluation of composites: internal quality of composites was evaluated via ultra-sonic C-scan (Omniscan MX2, Olympus Co., Taiwan).

Fig.1. Bagging method of extra-thick composite laminations.

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Table1. Curing cycles of extra-thick composite laminations

Laminations	Curing conditions*
16-1#、32-1#	Temperature ramp rate : 3 °C /min; Isothermal temperature:180 °C , hold time: 120min (recommended curing process).
16-2#、32-2#	Step 1:Temperature ramp rate : 3°C/min; Setting temperature:150°C; Step 2:Temperature ramp rate : 0.15°C/min; Hold time:60 min; Step3: Temperature ramp rate : 3°C/min; Isothermal temperature:180°C, hold time: 120min.
32-3#	Step 1:Temperature ramp rate : 3°C/min; Hold temperature:120°C; Step 2:Temperature ramp rate : 0.5°C/min; Holding time:60 min; Step3: Temperature ramp rate : 3°C/min; Isothermal temperature:180°C, hold time: 120min.

*all the laminations were heated up in autoclave from room temperature, after cured at 180 °C were cooled down to 30°C with 3°C/min.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Thermal analysis of prepregs

Curing character of a certain prepregs is crucial in determine the optimized processing cycle. In the present work, thermal curing behaviors of the epoxy matrixed prepregs was characterized by DSC analysis, and T_g (glass transition temperature) of the cured composite is 195.1 °C under the recommended curing process.

With the purpose to evaluating the affection of different curing cycles on the cured composites, DSC analysis has been conducted when different temperature holding platforms were introduced within the recommended curing cycle. The holding temperatures were set at 110, 120, 130,140 and 150 °C respectively, and holding time is 0.5 hours uniformly. All the curing cycles were finished in the DSC analysis instrument. T_g s of cured samples were also measured by DSC and the degree of curing can be compared based on the variation of T_g s.

T_g s of different cured samples were compiled in Table 2. Compared with recommended curing cycle, samples cured with isothermal holding platforms exhibits higher T_g s, are all above 199 °C, this is arbitrated to longer curing time within the whole curing cycles. Meanwhile T_g s of samples with isothermal holding platforms are almost the same, this suggests that different temperature holding platforms will not affect the final degree of curing.

Fig. 2. DSC curves of different process treatments

Fig. 3. DSC curves of cured prepreg samples

Table 2. T_g s of prepreg samples under different curing cycle process

Samples	Holding temperature /°C	Holding time /min	T_g /°C
1	-	-	195.10
2	110	30	199.08
3	120	30	199.23
4	130	30	199.74
5	140	30	199.83
6	150	30	199.98

3.2 Dynamic rheology analysis of prepregs

Rheology analysis can reflect the viscosity changing with temperature increase during resin curing process, therefore it is an accurate, convenient and flexible method to determine processing window of thermoset materials under different curing condition.

In this work, viscosity changing of prepreg was measured by dynamic rheology meter with temperature ramp rate of 3°C/min, and the curing processes are conducted as same as Table 2. The typical rheology behaviors of prepregs under recommended curing cycle was shown in Fig. 4, it can be seen that dynamic viscosities decreased gradually with increasing of the scanned temperatures started at 50 °C, then down to a valley stage where the melt viscosity reached the minimum point, and then went up with further increasing of the temperature due to the thermal curing of the epoxy resin. In Fig 5 low viscosity range started from 85 °C to the holding temperature platforms (110, 120, 130, 140 and 150°C). The viscosity increased from 2875 to 5368 Pa s when hold temperature is 110°C in 30 min, meanwhile from 2511 to 6178 Pa s when at 120°C. Therefore when isothermal at 140 and 150°C, viscosity increased dramatically. For instance, viscosity rised from 4510 to 37782 Pa s, this indicates when it is over 130°C, the crosslinking of epoxy resin reacts strongly and leads to high viscosity in a short period.

Fig. 4. Viscosity curves under recommended curing cycle.

Fig. 5. Viscosity curves with different curing processing

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3.3 In process temperature measuring, quality evaluation and curing cycle comparison

It often exhibits great temperature gradient cross the thickness of thick composite lamination because of low heat conductivity and heavy ply stacked. During the heating up stage of a curing cycle, internal section of the lamination is difficult to be heated up resulting in temperature lag compared with outer section of thick parts. Meanwhile when the curing reaction be initiated, heat easily accumulates at the internal section especially in the center. This will lead to the temperature abrupt elevating, or even over heated and combustion. All these factors will strongly affect the quality of cured composite. The thickness and lay-up sequence of composite are crucial in determining temperature gradient.

Based on thermal and dynamic rheology analysis, several experiments were conducted to achieve relatively uniform temperature distribution during the whole curing process. Taking curing temperature, processibility and manufacturing cost into consideration, two stages with lower heating rates at 120 and 150°C for 1 hour were chosen to optimize the recommended curing cycle. The temperature changings during curing process were in process measured and compared. The composite temperature of different sections was recorded using the average value of two thermal couples at the same position. And the thermal couples were numbered from 1 to 5 or 1 to 10, beginning from the interface of tooling and first ply of laminations.

3.3.1 Temperature distribution analysis of laminations with thickness of 16 mm

Under recommended curing condition, a lamination was cured and the temperature distribution across the thickness was recorded by thermal couples. The recommended curing cycle was shown in Table 1 and the temperature curve is depicted in Fig.6(16-1#). It can be seen in Fig. 6 all the temperature distributed in the rang from 177 to 188 °C at the very beginning of isothermal platform at 180 °C. Meanwhile temperate exhibited greatest difference in every ply where thermal couples were placed, especially in the first half of the isothermal platform (before 155 min), the biggest temperature difference is about 30 °C, which the bottom ply shown the highest temperature and center shown the lowest. However, in the second half the isothermal platform, all the plys seemed to incline to the same temperature. Viewed from the whole curing cycle, all the plys within the thick lamination, exhibited different curing history due to the great temperature discrepancy.

Aiming to decrease the temperature discrepancy, lower heating rate strategy was adopted. When the curing temperature reach 150 °C during recommended curing cycle (16-2# lamination), the heating up rate of 0.15°C /min was chosen and last time is 60 min, and then the heating rate was adjusted back to 3°C/min, until the curing temperature reached 180 °C holding at that temperature for 2 hours, and cooling down at 3°C/min. it can be seen in Fig. 7 within the lower heating rate stage, all the thermal couples exhibited almost the same temperatures due to the longer time for thermal equilibrium between different prepreg layers. Meanwhile when it came to the isothermal platform at 180 °C, the discrepancy of temperature cross the lamination were obviously smaller. The reason of applying lower heating rate at 150 °C is the most dramatically exothermal behavior was observed around this temperature according to the DSC analysis of prepreg samples, and lower cuing rate can make heat release smoothly and result in relatively more uniform temperature distribution.

Fig. 6. Temperature distribution of extra-thick lamination of 16-1#.

Fig. 7. Temperature distribution of extra-thick lamination of 16-2#.

3.3.2 Temperature distribution analysis of laminations with thickness of 32 mm

The temperature distribution of 32-1# lamination with thickness of 32 mm was depicted in Fig. 8. Obviously in the isothermal stage at 180 °C, all the temperature across the thickness increased dramatically due to strongly exotherm and heat accumulated in the lamination. Most thermal couple readings were above 200 °C, the highest temperature even reached 200 °C. To prevent overheated, an interruption of cooling operation was conducted, meantime the great nonuniformity of temperature between every thermal couples were observed in Fig 8.

When the lower heating rate stage which begins at 150 °C was applied for 32-2# lamination, the uniformity of temperature was improved (Fig. 9). However, in the very beginning of lower heating rate stage, the abrupt temperature ramping still exists attributing to the great thickness of composite. And during the isothermal stage, another great temperature ramping was observed. This indicates the heat within the thick composite can't reach a totally uniform state in the low heating rate stage. In the isothermal stage, the highest temperature is 184 °C, much lower than that under recommended curing cycle. Although the optimized curing cycle have improved the temperature uniformity, the overheated problem has not been solved yet.

Fig. 8. Temperature distribution of extra-thick lamination of 32-1#.

Fig. 9. Temperature distribution of extra-thick lamination of 32-2#.

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Another low heating rate strategy has been applied and evaluated (for 32-3# lamination), the lower heating rate was 0.5 °C/min when it reached 120 °C, and the lasting time was 60 min. it can be seen in the Fig. 10. overheated behavior was not observed during the lower heating rate stage. A very minor overheating appeared in the beginning of isothermal stage, and the biggest temperature discrepancy was observed at the same time, which ranged from 176 to 185 °C, it is very similar with 32-2# (which from 176 to 184 °C). This indicates that two optimized curing cycles exhibit the similar affection on diminishing the temperature discrepancy in the isothermal stage.

Fig. 10. Temperature distribution of extra-thick lamination of 32-3#.

Fig. 11. Temperature distribution of extra-thick lamination of 32-3# (enlarged in the isothermal stage).

3.4 Quality evaluation of extra-thick laminations

All the cured laminations were analyzed by ultrasonic C-scan, the C-scan graphs (derived from both transmitting and reflecting signal) were depicted in Fig. 11, (a) is 16-1#, (b) is 16-2# and (c) is 32-3#. Based on the graph (2) and (3) there is no obviously defect in each section in the areas without thermal couple wires embedded. Compared with 16-1# all the laminations exhibit major better uniform in ultrasonic singles, especially for graphs deriving from transmitting signals (left part of each picture), this indicates when the optimized curing cycle applied, both composites with thickness of 16 and 32 mm exhibit better internal quality than that with recommended curing cycle.

4. Conclusion

- (1) When different isothermal stages applied, curing degrees of cured composites increase, however there is no obviously discrepancy in affection on curing degrees between these isothermal stages.
- (2) Lower heating rate beginning at 150 °C can improve the temperature uniformity of lamination with 16mm thickness, and also can keep composite temperature in the bounds of the specified cure cycle.
- (3) Lower heating rate beginning at 120 °C can improve the temperature uniformity and overheated behavior of lamination with 32mm thickness.

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(4) Better internal quality can be achieved when optimized curing cycles applied compared with recommended curing cycle.

Fig. 12. C-scan graphs of 16-1#, 16-2# and 32-3#.

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